

ROBUST

CRISIS GOVERNANCE IN TURBULENT TIMES

Robust Governance during Turbulence. Overview of the Data from 35 Case Studies on Children’s Wellbeing During COVID-19

Authors of this deliverable: Emma Pullen, Maud Temmen, Marlot Kuiper and Scott Douglas (Utrecht University)

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Authors of case reports per country:

Belgium	Chiara Russo and Susana Coroado
Czechia	David Spaček
Denmark	Jacob Torfing, Tina Øllgaard Bentzen, Peter Triantafillou and Rasmus Øjvind Nielsen
Estonia	Eva Peeters
Hungary	Áron Hajnal and Gábor Tamás Molnár
Italy	Federico Cuomo
Norway	Alyssa Marie Kvalvaag, Ann-Torill Tørrisplass, Berit Irene Vannebo, Janne Paulsen Breimo and Christian Lo
Spain	Lourdes Torres, Vicente Pina, Lara Ripoll, Javier García-Lacalle and Jaime García-Rayado
The Netherlands	Emma Pullen, Maud Temmen, Marlot Kuiper and Scott Douglas

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Introduction

As turbulence and crises become more common in modern life, the European research project ROBUST explores the combinations of factors that promote or hinder robustness (Torfing et al., 2021). The project aspires to shift the focus of future crisis governance from concepts such as 'resilience' or 'agility' to prioritizing 'robustness' as a fundamental principle, highlighting the need for adaptive and innovative responses in turbulent times.

In ROBUST, a total of eighteen multi-layered, networked localities during the COVID-19 Crisis is studied with the aim of understanding how responses from actors at different levels (from EU bodies to local government) and from different domains (including public, private and community actors) interact. We examined 35 public value solutions, i.e. deliberate, targeted, enduring, cross-sectoral, cross-layer efforts, aimed at positively influencing child wellbeing in multi-layered networked localities during the pandemic.

The research project explores how three large governance factors enable the emergence of robust governance: multi-level governance, hybridity of governance, societal intelligence. Moreover, we focus on a set of actor-centered robustness strategies that may foster such robust responses. By combining both elements, we focus on the system-level while also studying actions of (groups of) individuals amidst societal turbulence. In Figure 1, we present the conceptual framework that is central to ROBUST, showcasing underlying assumptions based on earlier research.

Figure 1. Central conceptual model of the ROBUST project

Aim of this report

This reports combines three deliverables detailed in the ROBUST project plan, namely the D6.2 report on the independent variables in the public value solutions studied (governance factors thought to lead to robustness), the D6.3 report on the observed robustness attained by these public value solutions (split into effectiveness, legitimacy, innovativeness, adaptivity), and the D7.1 overall code data set which researchers can use for further analysis.

Although we planned on delivering the complete and coded dataset before providing a descriptive report on both the dependent and independent variables, the research process enables us to submit these all at once. As we used a detailed research protocol when gathering data as well as a strict format for the case reports in all localities, the data was already coded upon delivery. With support of the Project Officer, we therefore deliver these three deliverables in a combined report.

In the remainder of this document, we will present the cases and their context (part I). In part II, we describe the findings on the involved actors and the actor-centered robustness strategies. In part III the insights on the three large governance factors (multi-level governance, hybridity of governance, societal intelligence, D6.2) are showcased. Part IV consists of reflections on the outcome condition (robust governance, D6.3). Finally, in part V, we present the overall data set (D7.1).

Each section will start with a description of interesting and surprising findings, providing a short overview of the main observations for the variables that are central in the project. provides a descriptive overview – as rich as possible – of the data we have collected in ROBUST. To do so, we will emphasize averages, deviations, spread, and trends over time in the data. In presenting this overview, we will also explain what type of data we have collected and identify potential biases in our data. As outlined in the project plan, this report will not get to analyzing the configurations of data. That task will be completed at a later point in time, leading to a separate deliverable (D7.2).

Please consult the appendices, attached to this deliverable, for a complete overview of the data and the individual reports per multi-layered networked locality. By including these appendices, we aim to foster the transparency of our research while also offering other researchers the possibility to analyze the findings and answer related research questions. Moreover, we publish the reports on Zenodo to share the dataset with peer reviewers as well the Commission. These actors receive a password to access the platform. As soon as the ROBUST project comes to an end and publications are completed, the dataset will be un-embargoed. By then, it can be accessed by interested researchers and other stakeholders.

Part I. The cases and their context

1.1 Background information on case studies

To achieve the goals of ROBUST, we examined responses during the COVID-19 crisis across eighteen multi-layered, networked localities, spread over nine European countries. More specifically, we studied 35 public value solutions that were formulated and implemented to protect and foster child wellbeing during the pandemic. By doing so, we aimed to analyze how responses from various actors—ranging from EU institutions to local governments and encompassing public, private, and community sectors—interact, and how these collective actions are perceived by the public.

In the remainder of this document, we will present our findings by describing the results for different core concepts. Before doing so, we will delve into the (selection of the) public value solutions and in the data collection methods.

1.2 Public value solutions

A public value solution is defined as a deliberate, targeted, enduring, cross-sectoral, cross-layer effort to positively influence child wellbeing in the multi-layered networked locality. In ROBUST, a total of 35 public value solutions were studied (please consult Table 1 for a full list).

1.2.1 Selection of the public value solutions

The case selection process included several steps. First, contributing researchers selected the multi-layered networked localities, defined as “demarcated geographical spaces where the interaction between international, national, and local crisis responses can be observed, such as mid-sized cities or specific districts within large cities,” (Torfing et al., 2021, p. 15). Such localities can be illustrated by cities, districts within cities or towns. To foster comparability, the multi-layered networked localities that were selected had a population of 80.000 – 400.000 inhabitants.

Second, in each multi-layered networked locality, contributing researchers selected two public value solutions. In doing so, the researchers had to make sure the public value solutions were aimed at solving the problems that emerged due to COVID-19, and were sustained, or attempted to be sustained, between the outbreak of the pandemic and mid-2022. This focus on the full time series of COVID-19 enabled us to gather insights on temporal dynamics.

The criteria we established enabled us to select cases that were comparable while still exhibiting sufficient variation among them. However, there is a possibility that the selection leaned toward cases with robust outcomes. This is because such initiatives are often the ones known to the civil servants we interviewed and have received media attention. Furthermore, due to the local demarcation, mostly local initiatives were selected. Accordingly, our observations show that international and national actors are rarely involved compared to local actor. This, in turn, impacts the observations regarding (e.g.,) multi-level governance.

Please consult Table 1 for an full list of the solutions that were studied in ROBUST.

Country	Public value solution	Short description
Belgium	Initiatives focused on children's and family's mental wellbeing	This initiative focuses on promoting children's mental well-being through various activities. These include social media campaigns, distribution of materials, free short-term psychological support, and open-air festivals. Additionally, parents were supported through services on preventive health, child upbringing, and family network building. Vulnerable parents were contacted, outdoor group meetings for parents were organized, and play packages were distributed in collaboration with other actors.
Belgium	Support for vulnerable families and children and evaluating wellbeing and happiness of children	This solution addresses vulnerable children and families, assessing their well-being during the COVID-19 crisis. Activities include one-on-one conversations with youth, outdoor activities in small groups, open house afternoons, increased sports activities, and door-to-door package distribution. The Kortrijk health region also participated in the "A Healthy Mind in a Healthy Body" project, gathering data from 42 schools to assess happiness and nutrition, which helped guide local efforts.
Belgium	The 'oe-ist' initiative focused on understanding youngsters' wellbeing	The "oe-ist" (translated: "How is it?") initiative aimed to understand the well-being of youth during COVID-19. It involved a survey conducted twice during the pandemic, with the results shared with local partners to inform actions. Activities included promoting outdoor spaces for youth, offering project subsidies to schools to foster student connections, and organizing meetings with teachers.
Belgium	Emergency accommodation for children of parents doing essential jobs	This solution focused on providing emergency accommodation for children of parents working in essential roles. The goal was to ensure a safe environment while offering high-quality activities to develop children's cognitive, social, and psychological skills. Initially organized internally, this service was later expanded to involve other organizations to enhance service delivery and quality.
Czechia	E-schooling measures at three schools	This public value solution is about an approach to well-being of kids at 3 schools which have a

		higher share of kids from socially and economically disadvantaged families. Measures were focused on equipment for e-schooling (available to schools/teachers as well as kids).
Czechia	E-schooling measures, combined with social inclusion projects and protective measures	Within this public value solution ad-hoc, reactive measures were employed by schools, local NGOs and the local government organization, mostly focused on obtaining equipment for e-schooling (for schools and kids), distributing printed studying materials, gathering of protective equipment, distributing tools for testing, and communicating national measures and restrictions. Moreover, the public value solution consists of social inclusion projects and extra classes for some disadvantaged children.
Czechia	Unifying approaches at school and balancing e-schooling	This solution coordinated e-schooling across multiple schools by organizing regular meetings with school directors, consolidating information on legal requirements, sharing good practices, and providing support for additional teaching and e-schooling equipment.
Denmark	Outdoor learning garden	This public value solution focusses on a system for outdoor teaching to limit the spread of corona virus and be able to move around. After the re-opening of the schools, each class in a small school was provided a particular outdoor space. Over time this outdoor space developed into a 'learning garden' by support of the parents, teachers and children. Here, children learned other skills by participating in outdoor cooking and organizing a vegetable garden. Furthermore, over time the learning garden was equipped with teaching and sleeping facilities. Gradually, the learning garden was used by all classes at the school, an outdoor curriculum was developed and the garden could also be used by the local community that supports it in various ways.
Denmark	Outdoor drive-in cinema	This solution involved creating an outdoor drive-in cinema, allowing children, young people, and families to enjoy safe, distanced entertainment in their cars. The initiative, supported by the municipality, police, and volunteers, included

		performances by a local dance studio and contributed to the community's well-being.
Denmark	"Ungeliv", focused on supporting vulnerable youth	Ungeliv (Young Life) is a municipal service that supports vulnerable youth in Middelfart. In collaboration with 24 municipalities, it uses the Cyberhus digital platform to offer anonymous chats with advisors. These chats often lead to in-person meetings and referrals for intensive treatment. During the pandemic, the initiative also focused on how nature could support youth by fostering community and healing.
Denmark	Youth Well-Being Ambassadors	The Youth Well-Being Ambassadors initiative in Roskilde Municipality was launched by the Youth Council (8th-10th grade students) in 2020/21 to support student well-being after school closures. Each middle and secondary school (3rd-10th grade) trained two student-nominated ambassadors to promote inclusivity and organize activities. The training, provided by the social enterprise Play, aimed to foster engagement across all grades. There is no data on whether vulnerable children or immigrants were among the selected ambassadors.
Estonia	Measures for children with special educational needs	This initiative focused on students with special educational needs, allowing them to continue their education through physical meetings from the second wave of COVID-19. Special educators taught smaller groups, with stringent health protocols and, where possible, outdoor classes to minimize infection risks.
Estonia	Measures to provide access to library books and educational resources	During the COVID-19 lockdowns, Tallinn Central Library devised an innovative public value solution to ensure that citizens, particularly schoolchildren, had access to books and educational resources. This solution included measures as organizing online reading sessions, designed for children and by setting up contactless shelves where books could be picked up and returned without direct human interaction.
Estonia	Students helping schools as substitute teachers	This solution involved involving pedagogy students as assistant teachers in schools to alleviate the increased workload on teachers. These students assisted with IT support, student help, and preparation of online study materials.

		They were paid by the Ministry to support the educational system during the pandemic.
Estonia	Hot meals for children	In response to the closure of schools due to COVID-19, Tallinn implemented a public value solution to ensure all schoolchildren continued to receive their entitled free hot meals, recognizing that for some children, this might be their only hot meal of the day. These packages were compiled and delivered to schools with the help of volunteers. This initiative not only addressed biological needs by providing essential nutrition but also offered significant social benefits as many minors do not have access to a warm meal per day. Children had a reason to leave their homes periodically, maintaining a semblance of routine.
Hungary	Crisis Centre	This solution includes a Crisis Centre which was set up by the municipality. The purpose of the CC was to address the diverse needs of the municipality's residents related to the crisis. In practice, the Central Unit received calls and emails from residents requesting assistance in various domains. Next, the Central Unit assumed the role of a "matchmaker," seeking to address these needs to the greatest extent feasible by connecting individuals in need with volunteers, NGOs, and companies that had offered help, as well as municipal organizations. Specific child care related services included aid packages for deprived families, technical assistance for online teaching, tutoring and financial aid for deprived families.
Hungary	Mix of family-support services	This solution involved a mix of family-support services to safeguard children's development during the pandemic. It included information provision, crisis aid packages (food, toiletries), regular contact with families, and support services such as shopping for groceries, psychological help, and organizing events to reduce social isolation.
Hungary	Civil OEFF and Municipal OEFF	This public value solution, civil OEFF, comprises two interrelated yet distinct initiatives. Firstly, a small local NGO operated an on-site educational facility with municipal support during the first

		<p>wave of the pandemic. To increase the capacity of the OEEF, the municipality provided a larger venue and the necessary IT devices and facilitated the involvement of additional volunteers. Secondly, seeing the educational facility's success during the first wave and the problems related to online education, the municipality's leadership set up similar facilities at two other locations in May, named municipal OEEF. However, these were less successful.</p>
Hungary	<p>Activities of the Human Services Centre focused on online education assistance and harm reduction and prevention</p>	<p>This public value solution focusses on the Human Services Centre [MHS] of the Municipality who launched several novel activities and adjusted existing ones in order to assist local children, teachers, and educators with problems associated with online teaching [AOE], mainly through its Education Working Group [EWG]. Firstly, they provided direct assistance with online education. During school closures, employees of the EWG provided weekly online tutoring sessions in various subjects. Secondly, the EWG operated various activities/services aimed at harm reduction and harm prevention related to online education, such as excessive screen time and increased online presence.</p>
Italy	<p>Punto di Vista</p>	<p>Punto di Vista (PDV) is a project led by the Social Science Observatory of the Municipality of Ferrara in collaboration with the local healthcare agency, schools and cooperatives. It focusses on promoting the well-being of the school community and students by means of dialogue, workshops and psychological counselling activities. Apart from the activities with children, it also represented an educational counselling point for parents and teachers.</p>

Italy	The Scuola Diffusa initiative	With 'Scuola diffusa' (Widespread school), Reggio Emilia launched a relevant initiative aimed at designing and delivering alternative public spaces dedicated to teaching activities with elementary and middle schools. These venues included museums, community centres, civic buildings, farmhouses, and churches. Within those spaces, children were able to take advantage of learning technologies and alternative pedagogical materials provided by staff to delve into the artworks and artefacts on exhibition in the facilities.
Italy	A Casa con Il Reggio Approach	This public value solution consists of a multifunctional educational platform that provides children with a vast and heterogeneous set of multimedia and interactive products for distance learning.
Italy	Webinars for parents	This initiative offered webinars for parents to address the impact of COVID-19 on family dynamics. Topics included managing parent-child relationships, dealing with fake news, and understanding teenage behavior.
Norway	"Big City Youth-Help"	The idea behind the public value "Big City Youth-Help" is that if you feel that you could use help you may call the phone number for the initiative within your district and quickly receive an appointment. Some examples of topics they can assist with include child well-being, educational needs, and health challenges. "Big City Youth-Help" may provide families with advice and access to services regarding child development and need for additional services, without having to have official referrals to services. During COVID-19 the initiative was expanded and focused on helping with psychological services for youth.
Norway	"Youth Outreach"	The public value solution "Youth Outreach" has a special focus on youth that are at risk of developing problems related to social and mental well-being. The public value solution focuses on outreach work to meet youth where youth are. This involves getting out of the office and meeting youth on the streets, in shopping centers, at schools, and on Snapchat for

		example. This outreach work involves regular meetings over time to establish a presence in these environments. In addition to outreach work they provide individual counseling, conversations, and group work.
Norway	“A better school situation”	This solution, part of the municipal child welfare services, addresses serious school absenteeism by working closely with youth to develop individualized solutions, helping them set goals and work with social workers to achieve them.
Norway	“Big City Youth Forum”	The public value solution "Big City Youth Forum" aims to fill a gap as psychological health services are primarily focused on children or adults, while few services are targeted directly at youth and their needs. The forum took the format of drop-in service for young people between the ages of 12 and 25 years. The drop-in service is primarily focused on providing a place to have conversations with professionals when youth experience challenges and feel they need to discuss these challenges with someone. There is a short waiting time and there is no need for a referral from health professionals or other services to get help. Collaboration with other services is also key for "Big City Youth Forum", facilitating contact between youth and other services.
Spain	Family and children’s program	The family and children's program studied played a crucial role in helping to alleviate the problems created in vulnerable families. This program included emotional and psychological support to families, distributing food aid and basic resources and facilitating access to medical care, health, wellbeing, financial support and other services.
Spain	Summer camp	This public value solution includes a summer camp in which children of different ages with and without disabilities participate in group activities and games. It also serves as a solution for childcare during the non-school period when parents have to work and do not have other mechanisms to take care of their children.
Spain	Community entertainment	This public value solutions focusses on the program for community entertainment. This

		<p>program aims to educate in values (tolerance, respect, dialogue), to use play, as well as other activities (workshops, dynamics...) as a playful and pedagogical tool at the same time, to foster personal skills, to promote creativity and imagination, to offer various healthy and positive leisure time alternatives, to develop social skills, to complement the educational work of parents and educators in any social field, and to develop positive behavioral habits.</p>
Spain	Neighbourhood association	<p>This public value solution focusses on the facilitation of social services by a network of social organisations, schools and the local government to the community. The network created a complementary mechanism in which the people and organizations involved provided material and emotional support the kids and their families.</p>
The Netherlands	The living rooms	<p>In Deventer, so-called 'living rooms' were opened for vulnerable children. The target group consists of children who weren't able to attend a regular after-school care (e.g. due to lack of financial means in their family or behavioral difficulties). In the living room, children from the neighborhood meet each other, play together, and receive support where needed. Moreover, children have access to healthy meals in the living room. The program aims to provide a safe, nurturing environment for children who would otherwise lack access to structured after-school activities.</p>
The Netherlands	Recreational activities for youngsters	<p>This solution focuses on the offer of recreational activities for young people aged 10-14, organized by multiple NGOs in this locality. During the pandemic, these NGOs organized various activities, such as online events like an improvisation night, summer programs with diverse activities for children, numerous outdoor activities, and sport events in the summer for teenagers.</p>
The Netherlands	City network for equal opportunities	<p>This public value solution includes a network for academic support for children from disadvantaged backgrounds. Approximately 30 social and volunteer organizations are now</p>

		involved in this network, each offering various services for children. These services include activities designed to support and enhance children's learning, such as language buddies and homework assistance.
The Netherlands	Education for every youngster	This public value solution focusses on multiple initiatives to make education possible for every youngster. For example, by providing laptops to access e-education and by involving youth support workers, who were stationed in schools to identify and address preventive needs, escalating support when a child required different types of assistance.

Table 1. Full list of public value solutions.

The table demonstrates a wide range of public value solutions across diverse domains such as education, mental well-being, social support, and community engagement. These initiatives target various groups, including children, youth, families, and vulnerable populations. Educational solutions focus on e-learning support, substitute teachers, and creative teaching spaces. Mental health and social well-being initiatives offer psychological support, outreach services, and activities promoting social connection. Additionally, community-driven solutions provide essential resources, recreational activities, and innovative care models for disadvantaged groups. The solutions were mostly aimed at the entire population, with no visible distinction based on gender. However, there's one outlier, as one of the studied solutions is aimed at addressing gender-based violence.

1.3 Data collection

After having selected the public value solutions, contributing researchers were provided with an extensive research protocol. In this protocol, the data collection methods are described in-depth. Moreover, steps that needed to be taken to ensure the reliability and the validity of the data collection and analysis were set out, for example by including guidelines for intercoder reliability checks. All in all, the research protocol provided a step-by-step guide for researchers on how to carry out and report about their fieldwork.

To study the public value solutions, contributing scholars collected data from multiple sources. Mainly, they analyzed documents and conducted interviews. The analyzed documents consisted of (e.g.) newspaper articles, policy briefs, or progress reports. The interviews were organized with different types of respondents, coming from various (types of) organizations, from several levels: mostly local (such as municipal aldermen), regional (such as representatives from school boards), and national (such as national policy officers on education, sports, and youth topics) interviewees were involved. A gender-balanced recruitment of respondents was facilitated as we recognize the importance of inclusivity in our research process. Researchers involved were provided with an interview guide, including main questions as well as follow-up questions, covering the main concepts in ROBUST. To collect data on multi-level governance, for example, researchers were requested to pose questions such as “How would you describe the interaction between international, national,

regional, and local actors in the formulation and implementation of the initiative?”. To gather insights into societal intelligence and the accompanying knowledge interfaces, questions such as “In what setting and with what frequency did the different actors meet to exchange information and knowledge?” were included. By offering such guidelines on the main topics to discuss, and including possible follow-up questions in the interview guide, the researchers were provided with tools to bridge the gap between theoretical assumptions and real-life experiences.

The different types of data were collected between April 2024 and October 2024. Afterwards, involved researchers reported on their findings by submitting case reports. These reports, as well as the complete dataset, are attached to this deliverable (please consult the appendices).

Part II. Reports on the involved actors and the actor-centered robustness strategies

In this section of the report, we discuss the involvement of different types of actors from several levels, as well as the strategies they employed to boost child wellbeing during the COVID-19 pandemic. The results indicate that local actors played a key role in the initiatives that were studied, with a particular emphasis on the role of local governments. Local governments were frequently present and even crucial to the development and implementation of public value solutions during the pandemic. When looking at public sector professionals, we mostly see social (youth) workers and teachers being present throughout COVID-19 and even of significant importance in certain phases.

In terms of the deployment of different actor-centered robustness strategies in phases 1 and 2, an interesting pattern seems to emerge: *accountable autonomy* helps to provide a considerable room of maneuvering for actors on the ground, who then use this space to foster *distributive networks*, supported by *collaborative platforms*. The collaborating actors use *bricolage* to develop new solutions that in some, but not all, cases are tested through local *experimentation*.

When we move from phases 1 and 2 to the remainder of the pandemic, when the pressure from turbulence is lower and the new adaptive and innovative solutions become routinized, the need for using different actor-centered robustness strategies deteriorates, although the *accountable autonomy* allowing local collaboration continues to be important.

Based on the findings, the following questions could be addressed in the qualitative configurational analysis (QCA):

- To what extent and how did the involvement of local governments enhance the implementation and formulation of public value solutions during COVID-19, and how does this impact the robustness of public sector responses in times of turbulence?
- To what extent and how did the involvement of public service professionals, such as social (youth) workers and teachers, enhance the implementation and formulation of public value solutions during COVID-19, and how does this impact the robustness of public sector responses in times of turbulence?
- To what extent and how did the actor-centered robustness strategies of *promoting accountable autonomy* and *building distributed networks* contribute to the implementation and formulation of public value solutions during COVID-19, and how does this impact the robustness of public sector responses in times of turbulence?

2.1 Involved actors

Different types of actors were distinguished when studying the public value solutions in multi-layered networked localities. First, a distinction based on *levels* has been made, as we tried to capture whether actors from the international, national, regional, and/or local levels were involved in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions. Second, a distinction based on *domains* has been made, as we tried to capture whether market-actors, government-actors and/or NGOs were involved. Based on this distinction, actors potentially involved in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions during COVID-19 range from international emergency agencies to local governments and from national voluntary organizations to regional businesses.

The data shows mostly local governments and local NGOs were involved in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions. International, national and regional actors appear to play a less significant role. When it comes to the role of professional service professionals, we observe

social/youth workers and teachers are essential in the public value solutions that were examined. In the remainder of this section, we will report on the involved actors in more detail.

2.1.1 Involved actors on international level

In Figure 2, the extent to which international actors across various domains were involved in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 2. The average involvement of international actors in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing during the different phases of COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
International governments	0	0	0
International NGOs	0,10	0,10	0,09
International corporations	0,13	0,05	0

Table 2. Standard deviations for the involvement of international actors.

In Table 3, 4, 5, the involvement of international actors in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	35	35	35
0.33 (present)	0	0	0
0.66 (present and significant)	0	0	0
1 (present, significant and crucial)	0	0	0
Total	35	35	35

Table 3. The involvement of international governments in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	31	31	32
0.33 (present)	4	4	3
0.66 (present and significant)	0	0	0
1 (present, significant and crucial)	0	0	0
Total	35	35	35

Table 4. The involvement of international NGOs in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	32	34	35
0.33 (present)	2	1	0
0.66 (present and significant)	1	0	0
1 (present, significant and crucial)	0	0	0
Total	35	35	35

Table 5. The involvement of international corporations in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude the actor was present during the designing and/or the delivery of the public value solution throughout a specific phase (i.e., the actor was absent). Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution could not have come about without the input or involvement of the actor. The actor was present, significant and crucial. The findings show international actors were mostly absent in the formulation and implementation of the public value solutions that were examined. Throughout the phases, a minimal presence of international NGOs became visible. However, this only appears in a few cases. Moreover, in phase 1 and 2, such a marginal level of involvement of international corporations became visible as well. However, the results show no significant roles were played by international actors. Moreover, the standard deviation is small for the different types of actors (with a maximum of 0.1), indicating that the absence of international actors was a consistent pattern across the examined cases and throughout the different phases of the pandemic. Finally, the tables show a high level of stability over the course of the pandemic as well, confirming that the levels of involvement of international actors throughout the phases remained steady.

2.1.2 Involved actors on national level

In Figure 3, the extent to which national actors across various domains were involved in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 3. The average involvement of national actors in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing during the different phases of COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
National governments	0,30	0,30	0,30
National NGOs	0,27	0,29	0,29
National corporations	0,15	0,17	0,09

Table 6. Standard deviations for the involvement of national actors.

In Table 7, 8 and 9, the involvement of national actors in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	25	21	21
0.33 (present)	6	10	10
0.66 (present and significant)	1	1	1
1 (present, significant and crucial)	3	3	3
Total	35	35	35

Table 7. The involvement of national governments in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
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0 (absent)	26	24	24
0.33 (present)	6	6	6
0.66 (present and significant)	1	3	3
1 (present, significant and crucial)	2	2	2
Total	35	35	35

Table 8. The involvement of national NGOs in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	30	31	32
0.33 (present)	4	2	3
0.66 (present and significant)	1	2	0
1 (present, significant and crucial)	0	0	0
Total	35	35	35

Table 9. The involvement of national corporations in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude the actor was present during the designing and/or the delivery of the public value solution throughout a specific phase (i.e., the actor was absent). Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution could not have come about without the input or involvement of the actor. The actor was present, significant and crucial. The findings show national actors were mostly absent in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions. Although national governments, NGOs and corporations were minimally present in some cases, the results show they did not play a significant role in the public value solutions that were examined. The accompanying standard deviations imply that there is variety across cases. To illustrate, with a score of 0.30 for national governments, it appears their involvement varies over the studied public value solutions, and thus shows some level of inconsistency. Finally, the tables in which the spread is listed underscore a variety within the involvement of different types of national actors, while also showcasing stability in the (low level of) involvement of these governments, NGOs and corporations over the phases of COVID-19.

2.1.3 Involved actors on regional level

In Figure 4, the extent to which regional actors across various domains were involved in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 4. The average involvement of regional actors in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing during the different phases of COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
Regional governments	0,21	0,28	0,23
Regional NGOs	0,31	0,28	0,28
Regional corporations	0,20	0,18	0,18

Table 10. Standard deviations for the involvement of regional actors.

In Table 11, 12 and 13, the involvement of regional actors in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	22	21	23
0.33 (present)	10	8	8
0.66 (present and significant)	3	5	4
1 (present, significant and crucial)	0	1	0
Total	35	35	35

Table 11. The involvement of regional governments in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	25	26	26
0.33 (present)	5	5	6
0.66 (present and significant)	2	2	1
1 (present, significant and crucial)	3	2	2
Total	35	35	35

Table 12. The involvement of regional NGOs in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	29	32	32
0.33 (present)	5	2	2
0.66 (present and significant)	0	0	0
1 (present, significant and crucial)	1	1	1
Total	35	35	35

Table 13. The involvement of regional corporations in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude the actor was present during the designing and/or the delivery of the public value solution throughout a specific phase (i.e., the actor was absent). Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution could not have come about without the input or involvement of the actor. The actor was present, significant and crucial. The findings show regional actors were mostly absent in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions. Although regional governments, NGOs and corporations were minimally present in some cases, the results show they did not play a significant role in the public value solutions that were examined. The accompanying standard deviations imply that there is variety across cases. To illustrate, with a score of 0.31 for regional NGOs, it appears their involvement varies over the studied public value solutions, and thus shows some level of inconsistency. Finally, the tables in which the spread is listed underscore a variety within the involvement of different types of regional actors, while also showcasing stability in the (relatively low or minor level of) involvement of these governments, NGOs and corporations over the phases of COVID-19.

2.1.4 Involved actors on local level

In Figure 5, the extent to which local actors across various domains were involved in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 5. The average involvement of local actors in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing during the different phases of COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
Local governments	0,29	0,25	0,35
Local NGOs	0,42	0,41	0,41
Local corporations	0,39	0,40	0,37

Table 14. Standard deviations for the involvement of local actors.

In Table 15, 16, and 17, the involvement of local actors in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	2	1	4
0.33 (present)	3	3	3
0.66 (present and significant)	2	3	3
1 (present, significant and crucial)	28	28	25
Total	35	35	35

Table 15. The involvement of local governments in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	12	11	13
0.33 (present)	6	7	6
0.66 (present and significant)	5	6	6
1 (present, significant and crucial)	12	11	10
Total	35	35	35

Table 16. The involvement of local NGOs in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	17	21	21
0.33 (present)	9	5	7
0.66 (present and significant)	2	2	1
1 (present, significant and crucial)	7	7	6
Total	35	35	35

Table 17. The involvement of local corporations in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude the actor was present during the designing and/or the delivery of the public value solution throughout a specific phase (i.e., the actor was absent). Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution could not have come about without the input or involvement of the actor. The actor was present, significant and crucial. The findings show different types of local actors were present in the formulation and implementation of the public value solutions. On average, local NGOs and local corporations were present, whereas local governments were mostly deemed crucial. The accompanying standard deviations imply that there is a high level of variety across cases. To illustrate, with a score of 0.42 for local NGOs in the first phase, it appears their involvement varies to a high extent over the studied public value solutions, and thus shows a high level of inconsistency. Finally, the tables in which the spread is listed underscore this variety within the involvement of different types of local actors.

2.1.5 Involved public service professionals

In Figure 6, the extent to which public service professionals were involved in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 6. The average involvement of public service professionals in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing during the different phases of COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
Medical doctors	0,28	0,27	0,25
Public health experts	0,37	0,38	0,36
Psychologists	0,39	0,38	0,38
Teachers	0,38	0,37	0,38
Social/youth workers	0,36	0,31	0,36
Police officers	0,19	0,23	0,22
Academic researchers	0,17	0,24	0,22

Table 18. Standard deviations for the involvement of public service professionals.

In Tables 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, and 25, the involvement of different types of public service professionals in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	24	25	25
0.33 (present)	7	7	8
0.66 (present and significant)	2	1	0
1 (present, significant and crucial)	2	2	2
Total	35	35	35

Table 19. The involvement of medical doctors in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	21	21	21
0.33 (present)	5	4	4
0.66 (present and significant)	4	5	6
1 (present, significant and crucial)	5	5	4
Total	35	35	35

Table 20. The involvement of public health experts in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	18	18	21
0.33 (present)	7	8	6
0.66 (present and significant)	3	3	2
1 (present, significant and crucial)	7	6	6
Total	35	35	35

Table 21. The involvement of psychologists in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	9	8	9
0.33 (present)	6	5	6
0.66 (present and significant)	10	12	11
1 (present, significant and crucial)	10	10	9
Total	35	35	35

Table 22. The involvement of teachers in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	5	3	5
0.33 (present)	2	2	4
0.66 (present and significant)	7	9	8
1 (present, significant and crucial)	21	21	18
Total	35	35	35

Table 23. The involvement of social/youth workers in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	26	25	26
0.33 (present)	7	8	7
0.66 (present and significant)	2	1	1
1 (present, significant and crucial)	0	1	1
Total	35	35	35

Table 24. The involvement of police officers in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	30	28	28
0.33 (present)	3	2	3
0.66 (present and significant)	2	5	4
1 (present, significant and crucial)	0	0	0
Total	35	35	35

Table 25. The involvement of academic researchers in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude the actor was present during the designing and/or the delivery of the public value solution throughout a specific phase (i.e., the actor was absent). Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution could not have come about without the input or involvement of the actor. The actor was present, significant and crucial. The findings show how the involvement of specific groups of professionals remained relatively stable throughout the different phases of COVID-19. Moreover, police officers and academic researchers appear to have played a minor or no role at all, while social/youth workers and teachers were present and (in some phases) significant in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions. The accompanying standard deviations imply that there is a high level of variety across cases. To illustrate, with a score of 0.39 (phase 1) and 0.38 (phases 2 and 3) for psychologists, it appears their involvement varies to a high extent over the studied public value solutions, and thus shows a high level of inconsistency. Finally, the tables in which the spread is listed showcase that the involvement of different types of public service professionals differ over the cases but are relatively consistent across the phases of COVID-19.

Final reflection on confidence

Contributors deliver the outcomes regarding the involved actors with significant confidence (score: 0.82 on a scale of 0 to 1). Interesting to note is that the contributors have filled out a score of 0.66 or a score of 1; the data show that scores of 0 or 0.33 were not assigned. Therefore, confidence levels can be perceived as relatively high.

2.2 Actor-centered robustness strategies

2.2.1 Overall findings regarding actor-centered robustness strategies

Actor-centered robustness strategies are defined as “a set of evolving intentions and emergent actions contributing to creating conditions that support flexible and situated efforts to adapt and innovate for the purpose of responding to governance challenges in a manner that promotes both short-term and long-term effectiveness and legitimacy,” (Sørensen & Torfing, n.d., p. 6¹). In the ROBUST project, we identified nine actor-centered robustness strategies.

¹ Sørensen, E. & Torfing, J. (n.d.). *Robust public governance: political and administrative strategies*.

Figure 7 presents an integrated overview of the different strategies.

Figure 7. Integrated overview of actor-centered robustness strategies during COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
Building distributed networks	0,30	0,28	0,36

Scaling governance responses	0,38	0,39	0,29
Creating collaborative platforms	0,36	0,33	0,33
Planning for unexpected events and surprises	0,29	0,30	0,29
Exerting multi-vocality	0,37	0,35	0,28
Conducting experiments	0,38	0,37	0,30
Emerging of bricoleurs	0,33	0,35	0,30
Creating space for redundancy, slack and buffers	0,32	0,33	0,23
Promoting accountable autonomy	0,31	0,33	0,37

Table 26. Standard deviations for the employment of actor-centered robustness strategies.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a specific strategy was used for designing and/or delivering the public value solution throughout a specific phase (i.e., the strategy was absent). Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution could not have come about without a specific strategy. In that case, the strategy was present, significant and crucial. The findings show ‘building distributed networks’ and ‘promoting accountable autonomy’ were the only two strategies that had a significant impact on the formulation and implementation throughout the first and the second phase of COVID-19. The accompanying standard deviations imply that there is a high level of variety across cases, as these are ranging from 0.23 to 0.39 with most deviations being higher than 0.30. In the studied public value solutions, the employment of actor-centered robustness strategies thus varies to a high extent. In the sections that follow, we will elaborate on the findings per strategy.

2.2.2 Building distributed networks

Building distributed networks implies bringing together relevant and affected actors in loosely coupled arrangements, which may enhance learning, adaptation and innovation. In Figure 8, the employment of building distributed networks in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 8. The employment of building distributed networks in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing during COVID-19.

In Table 27, the employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	3	1	5
0.33 (present)	4	7	11
0.66 (present and significant)	15	12	7
1 (present, significant and crucial)	13	15	12
Total	35	35	35

Table 27. The employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a specific strategy was used for designing and/or delivering the public value solution throughout a specific phase (i.e., the strategy was absent). Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution could not have come about without a specific strategy. In that case, the strategy was present, significant and crucial. The findings show that, on average, this strategy was present and significant throughout the first two phases of the pandemic. During the remainder the strategy was present.

2.2.3 Scaling governance responses

Scaling governance responses implies bolstering the scope and volume of a particular solution up or down, which may help adapt solutions to shifting demands. In Figure 9, the employment of scaling

governance responses in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 9. The employment of scaling governance responses in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing during COVID-19.

In Table 28, the employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	8	9	12
0.33 (present)	8	6	17
0.66 (present and significant)	9	9	3
1 (present, significant and crucial)	10	11	3
Total	35	35	35

Table 28. The employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a specific strategy was used for designing and/or delivering the public value solution throughout a specific phase (i.e., the strategy was absent). Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution could not have come about without a specific strategy. In that case, the strategy was present, significant and crucial. The findings show that, on average, this strategy was present during the first and second wave of COVID-19, but played a smaller role in the remainder of the pandemic.

2.2.4 Creating collaborative platforms

Collaborative platforms are institutional or digital arenas that provide templates, knowledge, resource, communication tools etc. that make it easy to collaborate for flexible and innovative responses to turbulence. In Figure 10, the employment of creating collaborative platforms in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 10. The employment of creating collaborative platforms in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing during COVID-19.

In Table 29, the employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	6	4	9
0.33 (present)	9	12	15
0.66 (present and significant)	9	10	6
1 (present, significant and crucial)	11	9	5
Total	35	35	35

Table 29. The employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a specific strategy was used for designing and/or delivering the public value solution throughout a specific phase (i.e., the strategy was absent). Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution could not have come about without a specific strategy. In that case, the strategy was present, significant

and crucial. The findings show that, on average, this strategy was present throughout the different phases of COVID-19, and almost significant in the formulation and implementation of the public value solutions during the first two phases of the pandemic.

2.2.5 Planning for unexpected events and surprises

Planning for unexpected events and surprises means being vigilant by means of detecting and processing early signals of disruptive change, which may enable actors to be ready to deal with turbulence when it hits. In Figure 11, the employment of planning for unexpected events and surprises in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 11. The employment of planning for unexpected events and surprises in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing during COVID-19.

In Table 30, the employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	13	15	20
0.33 (present)	14	11	10
0.66 (present and significant)	6	7	3
1 (present, significant and crucial)	2	2	2
Total	35	35	35

Table 30. The employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per phase

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a specific strategy was used for designing and/or delivering the public value solution throughout a specific phase (i.e., the strategy was absent). Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution could not have come about without a specific strategy. In that case, the strategy was present, significant and crucial. The findings show that, on average, this strategy was present in many cases, especially in the first two phases of COVID-19, but did not have a significant or crucial impact on the formulation and implementation of the public value solutions that were studied.

2.2.6 Exerting multi-vocality

Exerting multi-vocality relates to producing and communicating vague, ambiguous and slightly different storylines to different audiences, which enables key decisionmakers to change problem understandings and solution strategies without losing support as they cannot be pinned to a fixed message. In Figure 12, the employment of exerting multi-vocality in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 12. The employment of exerting multi-vocality in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing during COVID-19.

In Table 31, the employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	17	16	18
0.33 (present)	7	7	10
0.66 (present and significant)	6	8	6
1 (present, significant and crucial)	5	4	1
Total	35	35	35

Table 31. The employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a specific strategy was used for designing and/or delivering the public value solution throughout a specific phase (i.e., the strategy was absent). Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution could not have come about without a specific strategy. In that case, the strategy was present, significant and crucial. The findings show that, on average, this strategy was nearly present during the first two phases of COVID-19. However, throughout the pandemic, this strategy did not have a significant impact on the formulation and implementation of public value solutions.

2.2.7 Conducting experiments

Conducting experiments implies iterative rounds of prototyping, experimental testing, evaluation and revision, enabling fast learning that in turn spurs adaptation and innovation. In Figure 13, the employment of conducting experiments in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 13. The employment of conducting experiments in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing during COVID-19.

In Table 32, the employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	14	13	17
0.33 (present)	9	9	10
0.66 (present and significant)	5	7	6
1 (present, significant and crucial)	7	6	2
Total	35	35	35

Table 32. The employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a specific strategy was used for designing and/or delivering the public value solution throughout a specific phase (i.e., the strategy was absent). Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution could not have come about without a specific strategy. In that case, the strategy was present, significant and crucial. The findings show that, on average, this strategy was present in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions, only during the first two phases of COVID-19.

2.2.8 Emerging of bricoleurs

Bricolaging implies reusing, recombining and repurposing already existing tools and modular structures as a way of ensuring adaptation. In Figure 14, the employment of brocilage in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 14. The employment of bricolage in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing during COVID-19.

In Table 33, the employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	4	7	11
0.33 (present)	9	6	11
0.66 (present and significant)	12	14	11
1 (present, significant and crucial)	10	8	2
Total	35	35	35

Table 33. The employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a specific strategy was used for designing and/or delivering the public value solution throughout a specific phase (i.e., the strategy was absent). Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution could not have come about without a specific strategy. In that case, the strategy was present and significant. The findings show that, on average, bricolage was present and almost had a significant impact on the formulation and implementation of public value solutions during the first two phases of the pandemic. In the remainder of COVID-19, this strategy remained present but did not have a significant impact anymore.

2.2.9 Creating space for redundancy, slack and buffers

Creating space for redundancy, slack and buffers means having extra or excess resources, enabling actors to find the means to reduce the impact of turbulence and craft adaptive and innovative responses.

In Figure 15, the employment of creating space for redundancy, slack and buffers in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 15. The employment of creating space for redundancy, slack and buffers in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing during COVID-19.

In Table 34, the employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	18	20	24
0.33 (present)	12	7	7
0.66 (present and significant)	1	5	4
1 (present, significant and crucial)	4	3	0
Total	35	35	35

Table 34. The employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a specific strategy was used for designing and/or delivering the public value solution throughout a specific phase (i.e., the strategy was absent). Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution could not have come about without a specific strategy. In that case, the strategy was present, significant and crucial. The findings show that, on average, this strategy was rarely employed, especially during the remainder of COVID-19.

2.2.10 Promoting accountable autonomy

Robustness can be achieved by granting local governance actors some degree of independence to respond in a flexible and timely fashion to unforeseen and uncertain developments while observing some general goals and guidelines that they are accountable for. In Figure 16, the promotion of accountable autonomy in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 16. The promotion of accountable autonomy in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing during COVID-19.

In Table 35, the employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	3	4	7
0.33 (present)	4	3	3

0.66 (present and significant)	14	13	12
1 (present, significant and crucial)	14	15	13
Total	35	35	35

Table 35. The employment of this actor-centered robustness strategy per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a specific strategy was used for designing and/or delivering the public value solution throughout a specific phase (i.e., the strategy was absent). Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution could not have come about without a specific strategy. In that case, the strategy was present, significant and crucial. The findings show that, on average, this strategy was present and significant during the first two phases of COVID-19. In the remainder of the pandemic, averages show that this strategy remained present but did not have a significant impact on the formulation and implementation of public value solutions anymore. However, please note that in a relatively large number of studied public value solutions, the strategy continued to be present and significant, and even had a crucial impact in many cases.

Final reflection on confidence

Contributors deliver the outcomes regarding the involved actors with significant confidence (score: 0.82 on a scale of 0 to 1). Interesting to note is that the contributors have filled out a score of 0.66 or a score of 1; the data show that scores of 0 or 0.33 were not assigned. Therefore, confidence levels can be perceived as relatively high.

Part III. Reports on the multi-level governance, hybrid governance, and societal learning in the localities (D6.2)

3.1 Multi-Level Governance

A multi-level governance arrangement is defined as “an arrangement or process that presents three key features: 1) different levels of government are simultaneously involved; 2) non-governmental actors at different levels are also involved; 3) relationships defy existing hierarchies and take the form of non-hierarchical networks,” (Caponio et al., 2023, p. 25).²

Taking into account the three key features of multi-level governance, the involvement of non-governmental actors occurs with more frequency than the involvement of different governmental levels and the adoption of non-hierarchical relationships within multi-level governance arrangements or venues.

Across the phases of the pandemic, in the majority of studied public value solutions (18 out of 35), the involvement of non-governmental actors is present, crucial and significant. Meanwhile, the standard deviation is higher in the involvement of non-governmental actors than in the other two features of the multi-level governance arrangements.

Regarding the non-governmental actors' involvement, the amount of variation reaches its maximum value (0.39) in the first two phases. Different governmental levels are more involved in the first two phases of the COVID-19 response (0.34) than in the remainder (0.33). The presence of a non-hierarchical approach within the arrangements peaks in the first phase and remainder, while a brief decrease is evident in the second phase.

Regarding multi-level governance venues, i.e. physical or online meetings where all actors engaged in decision-making processes come together, bilateral meetings are the collaborative sites that most often host multi-level governance. However, those meetings are characterized by a decreasing trend, occurring more frequently in the first phase of response to COVID-19. The appearance of formal groups was mainly present in the second phase of the pandemic, although on average it never reached significant levels. Less formalized groups, on the other hand, emerged more frequently, being present especially in the first phase. ad hoc workshops are frequently absent and did not have a significant impact on the formulation and implementation of public value solutions.

Based on the findings, the following questions could be addressed in the qualitative configurational analysis (QCA):

- An interesting aspect concerns the type of involvement of non-governmental actors. Although this characteristic emerges frequently, it is often not necessarily accompanied by the adoption of a non-hierarchical approach. This raises questions about the nature of cooperation of non-governmental actors, how they are involved when hierarchical dynamics persist, and whether these affect the ability of arrangements to stimulate robust governance strategies.
- Another critical aspect concerns the involvement of different levels of government. What are the most common institutional configurations, namely which governmental levels are more frequently involved in multi-level governance?
- Finally, with regard to venues, it could be relevant to investigate why more flexible venues, such as bilateral meetings or non-formalized groups, appear to be more suitable for multi-

² Caponio, T., Ravazzi, S., & Pettrachin, A., (2023, August 25). *Ideal typology of Multilevel Governance strategies*.

level governance arrangements. In this sense, focus can also be on the role of such venues in providing robust governance amidst societal turbulence.

3.1.1 Multi-level governance arrangements

A multi-level governance arrangement is defined as “an arrangement or process that presents three key features: 1) different levels of government are simultaneously involved; 2) non-governmental actors at different levels are also involved; 3) relationships defy existing hierarchies and take the form of non-hierarchical networks,” (Caponio et al., 2023, p. 25).³ In Figure 17, the appearance of multi-level governance arrangements in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 17. Multi-level governance arrangements in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions during COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

³ Caponio, T., Ravazzi, S., & Pettrachin, A., (2023, August 25). *Ideal typology of Multilevel Governance strategies*.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
Involvement of different governmental levels	0,34	0,34	0,33
Involvement of non-governmental actors	0,39	0,39	0,37
Non-hierarchical relationships within the arrangements	0,33	0,35	0,34

Table 36. Standard deviations for the key features of multi-level governance.

In Figure 18, 19, and 20, the averages of the three key features of multi-level governance arrangements over the three phases is visually displayed.

Figure 18. Averages of scores regarding the involvement of different governmental levels in multi-level governance arrangements (key feature 1) over the three phases of COVID-19.

In Table 37, the involvement of different governmental levels per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	11	13	15
0.33 (present)	14	7	9
0.66 (present and significant)	5	12	8
1 (present, significant and crucial)	5	3	3
Total	35	35	35

Table 37. The involvement of different governmental levels per phase.

Figure 19. Averages of scores regarding the involvement of non-governmental actors in multi-level governance arrangements (key feature 2) over the three phases of COVID-19.

In Table 38, the involvement of different non-governmental actors per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	6	6	5
0.33 (present)	6	5	6

0.66 (present and significant)	5	6	6
1 (present, significant and crucial)	18	18	18
Total	35	35	35

Table 38. The involvement of different non-governmental actors per phase.

Figure 20. Averages of scores regarding the non-hierarchical relationships in multi-level governance arrangements (key feature e) over the three phases of COVID-19.

In Table 39, the presence of non-hierarchical relationships per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	8	10	9
0.33 (present)	9	7	7

0.66 (present and significant)	13	13	14
1 (present, significant and crucial)	5	5	5
Total	35	35	35

Table 39. The presence of non-hierarchical relationships per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude (certain characteristics within) multi-level governance arrangements were used for designing and/or delivering public value solutions throughout a specific phase. Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude public value solutions could not have come about without (certain characteristics within) the multi-level governance arrangements. In that case, the (characteristics within) multi-level governance arrangements were present, significant and crucial.

The findings show that the *vertical* dimension of multi-level governance, i.e. ‘involvement of different governmental levels’, is present throughout the different phases of COVID-19. If we take a more detailed look at this key feature, we find that this average is the result of relatively large differences over the cases: in some public value solutions, the involvement of different governmental levels was crucial, while in other cases, the different levels were not even represented in the formulation and implementation of the initiatives. The standard deviations confirm this finding.

Moreover, the *horizontal* dimension of multi-level governance, i.e., ‘involvement of non-governmental actors’, is present and significant throughout the different phases of COVID-19 (on average). The findings show that, in the formulation and implementation of the majority of the public value solutions, the involvement of non-governmental actors was even crucial. However, please note that this is accompanied by relatively high standard deviations.

Finally, averages scores on the feature of non-hierarchical relationships within the multi-level governance arrangements show that, on average, these relationships appear and are continuously present. When we take a more detailed look, we observe that the relationships can be defined as non-hierarchical for a large part of the cases. However, some outliers can be found in the data. I.e., in some cases, the non-hierarchical characteristic is absent, while in other cases, it is deemed crucial. This finding is confirmed by relatively high standard deviations as well.

3.1.2 Venue: bilateral meetings

A venue is a physical or digital space where actors from multi-level governance arrangements get together for decision making. In the venues, involved actors meet and discuss what to implement and how to do so. A bilateral meeting is a physical or digital space where two different partners get together. In Figure 21, the appearance of bilateral meetings in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 21. The appearance of bilateral meetings for formulating and implementing public value solutions during COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0,32	0,30	0,34

Table 40. Standard deviations for this venue.

In Table 41, the appearance of this venue per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	3	2	4
0.33 (present)	6	8	9
0.66 (present and significant)	12	12	10
1 (present, significant and crucial)	14	13	12
Total	35	35	35

Table 41. The appearance of this venue per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a certain venue was used for designing and/or delivering the public value solution in a specific phase of COVID-19. Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude that the public value solution could not have come about without a certain venue. In that case, the venue was present, significant and crucial. The findings

show how bilateral meetings were present throughout the different phases of COVID-19, and had a significant impact on the formulation and implementation of public value solutions in the first and second wave of the pandemic. However, please note that these interpretations are based on average scores, which are accompanied by relatively high standard deviations. Therefore, the extent to which there is a variety across cases is relatively high.

3.1.3 Venue: formalized groups

A venue is a physical or digital space where actors from multi-level governance arrangements get together for decision making. In the venues, involved actors meet and discuss what to implement and how to do so. In the venues, involved actors meet and discuss what to implement and how to do so. In formalized groups, governmental and non-governmental actors are in charge of attending regular meetings, with shared rules, to discuss about common goals and modes of public value solutions. Their attendance is predefined and formalized. Examples of these formalized groups are standing committees or joint commissions. In Figure 22, the appearance of formalized groups in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 22. The appearance of formalized groups for formulating and implementing public value solutions during COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0,36	0,38	0,37

Table 42. Standard deviations for this venue.

In Table 43, the appearance of this venue per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	15	14	14
0.33 (present)	8	9	10
0.66 (present and significant)	7	5	5
1 (present, significant and crucial)	5	7	6
Total	35	35	35

Table 43. The appearance of this venue per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a certain venue was used for designing and/or delivering the public value solution in a specific phase of COVID-19. Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude that the public value solution could not have come about without a certain venue. In that case, the venue was present, significant and crucial. The findings show how formalized groups were present throughout the different phases of COVID-19 but did not have a significant impact on the formulation and implementation of public value solutions. However, please note that these interpretations are based on average scores, which are accompanied by relatively high standard deviations. Therefore, the extent to which there is a variety across cases is relatively high.

3.1.4 Venue: less formalized group gatherings

A venue is a physical or digital space where actors from multi-level governance arrangements get together for decision making. In the venues, involved actors meet and discuss what to implement and how to do so. Less formalized group gatherings are meetings or thematic tables open to the public where governmental and non-governmental actors at different levels of governance, as well as experts and eventually citizens, discuss public value solutions. In less formalized group gatherings, the composition of the actors and the modes of interaction are not predefined. An example could be a conference that is open to the public. In Figure 23, the appearance of less formalized group gatherings in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 23. The appearance of less formalized group gatherings for formulating and implementing public value solutions during COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0,40	0,38	0,39

Table 44. Standard deviations for this venue.

In Table 45, the appearance of this venue per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	9	9	12
0.33 (present)	7	7	8
0.66 (present and significant)	7	10	7
1 (present, significant and crucial)	12	9	8
Total	35	35	35

Table 45. The appearance of this venue per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a certain venue was used for designing and/or delivering the public value solution in a specific phase of COVID-19. Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude that the public value solution could not have come about without a certain venue. In that case, the venue was present, significant and crucial. The findings

show how less-formalized group gatherings were present throughout the different phases of COVID-19, but did not a significant impact on the formulation and implementation of public value solutions. However, please note that these interpretations are based on average scores, which are accompanied by relatively high standard deviations. Therefore, the extent to which there is a variety across cases is relatively high.

3.1.5 Venue: ad hoc workshops

A venue is a physical or digital space where actors from multi-level governance arrangements get together for decision making. In the venues, involved actors meet and discuss what to implement and how to do so. In the venues, involved actors meet and discuss what to implement and how to do so. In ad hoc workshops, public and non-public actors from different levels of governance meet to discuss a specific issue or topic, usually coordinated by facilitators or chairs. For these ad hoc workshops, certain members are invited, and the roles of these participants are clear beforehand. Ad hoc workshops are narrow in scope and, therefore, the agendas are predefined as well. The aim of these ad hoc workshops is to produce shared proposals for public value solutions. In Figure 24, the appearance of ad hoc workshops in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 24. The appearance of ad hoc workshops for formulating and implementing public value solutions during COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
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0,32	0,34	0,32
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Table 46. Standard deviations for this venue.

In Table 47, the appearance of this venue per case is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	17	16	17
0.33 (present)	8	5	7
0.66 (present and significant)	8	12	9
1 (present, significant and crucial)	2	2	2
Total	35	35	35

Table 47. The appearance of this venue per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a certain venue was used for designing and/or delivering the public value solution in a specific phase of COVID-19. Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude that the public value solution could not have come about without a certain venue. In that case, the venue was present, significant and crucial. The findings show how ad hoc workshops were present in the second phase of COVID-19, but did not a significant impact on the formulation and implementation of public value solutions. However, please note that these interpretations are based on average scores, which are accompanied by relatively high standard deviations. Therefore, the extent to which there is a variety across cases is relatively high.

Final reflection on confidence

Contributors deliver the outcomes regarding multi-level governance with significant confidence (score: 0.83 on a scale of 0 to 1). Interesting to note is that the contributors have filled out a score of 0.66 or a score of 1; the data show that scores of 0 or 0.33 were not assigned. Therefore, confidence levels can be perceived as relatively high.

3.2 Hybridity of Governance

Hybridity of governance refers to “a configuration of coordinated decision-making and implementation through designing and managing sound combinations of ideal types to achieve the most suitable outcomes (Meuleman 2019; Sørensen and Torfing 2019)” (Nõmmik et al., 2023, p. 7).⁴

The averages and spread of the findings indicate the significance of network-based instruments. The average and spread for the hierarchical approach suggests that it adopts different roles for crisis response. Several cases highlight its presence, yet limited significance, which may indicate their supportive role through structures and policies, where network and market approaches are primarily utilized. In other public value solutions, it is more significant, which suggests that the hierarchical approach adopted a more dominant role through the use of command and control.

Whilst market-based approaches were present only for a limited amount of public value solutions, the spread indicates that their role within the public value solutions was significant. This indicates that market-based instruments, e.g. incentives and contractual relations for provision of services and infrastructure, become a viable alternative for steering competencies and resources in certain conditions.

Due to the high levels of variability with the approaches, it is interesting to analyze the different configurations and their complementing dynamics to understand, which configurations are conducive to which robustness strategies and the reflections on robustness.

Based on the findings, other questions that could be addressed in the qualitative configurational analysis (QCA) are related to the following topics:

- One of the more interesting findings relates to the lack of criticisms for the selected governance approaches. Despite the variation in the presence and configuration of governance approaches, the cases highlighted either the absence or only limited challenges with providing input, transparency of the process or effectiveness. For example, despite a significance of network-based approaches, actors reported limited criticisms regarding effectiveness or transparency of the process. This dynamic may originate from a variety of factors, which highlights opportunities for further (configurational) analyses.
- Another interesting finding is related to the selection of the governance measures and dynamics between governance approaches. The findings suggest a significant role for pre-crisis governance structures, presence and significance of past policy reforms for selecting governance measures. This significance continues over time. This suggests that the structures and processes present within the policy area prior to the crisis have a crucial role throughout a slow burning crisis. The stability of the chosen governance approaches can originate from a number of factors, worthy of further analysis.

3.2.1 Three different approaches

Although we will present the findings per governance approach in the upcoming sections, figure 25 presents an integrated overview of the different governance approaches. The hierarchical approach of governance relies on legitimate authority, involving the use of management and structural instruments to establish a more direct control to achieve goals.³ The market-based approach of governance relies on instruments focused on incentivization towards specific outputs and

⁴ Nõmmik, S., Coroado, S.D., Verhoest, K., & Randma-Liiv, T., (2023, August 31). *Framework for studying hybridity during crises*.

measurement of actions.³ The network approach of governance relies on the use of solidarity and interdependency through process-related instruments that aim to provide space for interactions.³

Figure 25. Integrated overview of governance approaches during COVID-19.

The averages, as shown in the figure above, are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
Hierarchical approach of governance	0,30	0,33	0,28
Market-based approach of governance	0,32	0,36	0,31
Network approach of governance	0,31	0,30	0,36

Table 48. Standard deviations for the different governance approaches.

In Figure 26, 27, and 28, the averages of the three governance approaches over the three phases is visually displayed.

Figure 26. Averages of the hierarchical approach over the three phases of COVID-19.

In Table 49, the appearance of the hierarchical approach is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	2	6	8
0.33 (present)	15	13	19
0.66 (present and significant)	10	9	5
1 (present, significant and crucial)	8	7	3
Total	35	35	35

Table 49. The appearance of the hierarchical approach of governance per phase.

Figure 27. Averages of the market-based approach over the three phases of COVID-19.

In Table 50, the appearance of the market-based approach is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	21	18	20
0.33 (present)	5	5	6
0.66 (present and significant)	7	8	7
1 (present, significant and crucial)	2	4	2
Total	35	35	35

Table 50. The appearance of the market-based approach of governance per phase.

Figure 28. Averages of the network approach over the three phases of COVID-19.

In Table 51, the appearance of the network approach is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	3	3	6
0.33 (present)	2	2	5
0.66 (present and significant)	11	13	12
1 (present, significant and crucial)	19	17	12
Total	35	35	35

Table 51. The appearance of the network approach of governance per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a certain approach of governance was used for designing and/or delivering public value solutions throughout a specific phase. In that case, the approach was absent. Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude that public value solutions could not have come about without a specific approach of governance. In that case, the approach was present, significant and crucial.

The integrated overview showcases how the network-based approach of governance was predominant throughout the different phases of COVID-19. When we take a more detailed look, we

observe this network approach was, on average, significant or even crucial in the majority of the cases that were examined. On the contrary, the market-based approach seems to be absent in the formulation and implementation of half of the public value solutions that were studied. However, we observe some outliers where this approach of governance was present or even significant. Finally, when it comes to the hierarchical approach of governance is present in a large majority of the public value solutions, with some cases in which this approach is deemed significant or even crucial. Please note that these interpretations are based on averages, which are accompanied by relatively high standard deviations. Therefore, the extent to which there is a variety across cases is relatively high.

3.2.2 Reasons for selection of governance approaches

The selection for governance approaches can be based on pre-crisis governance structures, past policy or reform failures and/or successes, the legislative framework, urgency due to the crisis, a lack of resources, stakeholder interests, and divergent interpretations amongst engaged actors. In Figure 29, the reasons for selecting governance approaches in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 29. The reasons for selecting governance approaches in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing during COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
Precrisis governance structure	0,36	0,36	0,37
Past policy reform failures or successes	0,37	0,38	0,37
Legislative framework	0,37	0,35	0,30

Urgency due to the crisis	0,40	0,37	0,32
Lack of resources	0,37	0,29	0,25
Stakeholder interests	0,33	0,34	0,35
Divergent interpretations amongst engaged actors	0,16	0,17	0,17

Table 52. Standard deviations for the reasons for the selection of governance approaches.

In Tables 53, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, and 59, the different reasons for the selection of governance approaches are listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	6	6	8
0.33 (present)	5	5	4
0.66 (present and significant)	11	12	13
1 (present, significant and crucial)	13	12	10
Total	35	35	35

Table 53. The influence of the precrisis governance structure on the selection of governance approaches in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	9	12	15
0.33 (present)	7	4	5
0.66 (present and significant)	11	12	10
1 (present, significant and crucial)	8	7	5
Total	35	35	35

Table 54. The influence of past policy reform failures or successes on the selection of governance approaches in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	10	12	17
0.33 (present)	11	11	11
0.66 (present and significant)	6	7	5
1 (present, significant and crucial)	8	5	2
Total	35	35	35

Table 55. The influence of the legislative framework on the selection of governance approaches in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	9	11	18
0.33 (present)	2	8	10
0.66 (present and significant)	10	9	4
1 (present, significant and crucial)	14	7	3
Total	35	35	35

Table 56. The influence of urgency due to the crisis on the selection of governance approaches in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
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0 (absent)	17	20	21
0.33 (present)	7	7	8
0.66 (present and significant)	6	7	6
1 (present, significant and crucial)	5	1	0
Total	35	35	35

Table 57. The influence of the lack of resources on the selection of governance approaches in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	11	12	14
0.33 (present)	5	3	5
0.66 (present and significant)	16	17	13
1 (present, significant and crucial)	3	3	3
Total	35	35	35

Table 58. The influence of stakeholder interests on the selection of governance approaches in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	27	26	26
0.33 (present)	7	8	8
0.66 (present and significant)	1	1	1
1 (present, significant and crucial)	0	0	0
Total	35	35	35

Table 59. The influence of divergent interpretations amongst engaged actors on the selection of governance approaches in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a certain approach of governance was used because of a certain phenomenon. Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude that the choice for a certain approach of governance could not have come about without a certain phenomenon. In that case, the phenomenon was present, significant and crucial. The findings show that, on average, pre-crisis governance structures, past policy reform successes and/or failures, legislative frameworks, urgency due to the crisis and stakeholder interests were present and significant throughout the different phases of COVID-19. Therefore, the results showcase how these factors are the main reasons for selecting certain governance approaches. However, please note that these interpretations are based on averages, which are accompanied by relatively high standard deviations. Therefore, the extent to which there is a variety across cases is relatively high.

3.2.3 Criticism on selected governance approaches

The criticism on the selected governance approaches is based on actors being (un)able to provide (sufficient) input, perceptions of (un)transparency and (un)fairness, and perceptions of (in)effectiveness by actors. In Figure 30, the types of criticism on selected governance approaches in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions is visually displayed.

Figure 30. The types of criticism on selected governance approaches in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing during COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
Relevant actors not being involved or being unable to provide (sufficient) input	0,21	0,23	0,23
Perceptions of untransparency or unfairness by relevant actors	0,14	0,15	0,12
Perceptions of ineffectiveness by relevant actors	0,20	0,21	0,20

Table 60. Standard deviations for criticism on the selected governance approaches.

In Tables 61,62 and 63, the different types of criticism on the selected governance approaches are listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	25	24	28
0.33 (present)	7	9	4
0.66 (present and significant)	3	1	2
1 (present, significant and crucial)	0	1	1
Total	35	35	35

Table 61. The criticism of actors not being involved or being unable to provide (sufficient) input in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	31	30	30
0.33 (present)	3	4	5
0.66 (present and significant)	1	1	0
1 (present, significant and crucial)	0	0	0
Total	35	35	35

Table 62. The perceptions of untransparency or unfairness in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	28	26	27
0.33 (present)	6	8	7
0.66 (present and significant)	0	0	0
1 (present, significant and crucial)	1	1	1
Total	35	35	35

Table 63. The perceptions of ineffectiveness by relevant actors in the formulation and implementation of public value solutions regarding child wellbeing per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a certain approach of governance was used because of a certain type of criticism. Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude that the choice for a certain approach of governance could not have come about without a specific type of criticism. In that case, the type of criticism was present, significant and crucial. The findings show that different types of criticism did not have a (significant or crucial) impact on the selection of specific governance approaches in the different phases of COVID-19. Please note that these interpretations are based on averages, which are accompanied by relatively moderate to high standard deviations. Therefore, there is variety across cases.

Final reflection on confidence

Contributors deliver the outcomes regarding hybridity of governance approaches with significant confidence (score: 0.79 on a scale of 0 to 1). Interesting to note is that the contributors have filled out a score of 0.66 or a score of 1; the data show that scores of 0 or 0.33 were not assigned. Therefore, confidence levels can be perceived as relatively high.

3.3 Societal Intelligence

Societal intelligence is defined as “the capacity to make decisions informed by different types of knowledge whose epistemology is identifiable by the actors involved,” (Russo & Van Dooren, 2023, p. 5⁵). This paragraph discusses the key outcomes that are derived from the analysis regarding societal intelligence.

Firstly, in terms of knowledge types, the average involvement of political knowledge declines through the phases of the crisis (Figure 31). The spread of political knowledge through the phases tells us the same story, as political knowledge gets less and less present and significant throughout the crisis (Table 66). Expert and lifeworld knowledge, in fact, both increase in average involvement in Phase 2 of the crisis. Expert knowledge is present in most cases, but significant or crucial only in a few. On the other hand, the findings on lifeworld knowledge are surprising. Lifeworld knowledge is on average the most present (Figure 32) and it appears to be crucial on average in twelve public value solutions (Figure 34). The spread of this knowledge type also confirms it to be crucial throughout the three phases of the crisis (Table 67).

Turning to findings on knowledge interfaces, it seems that, on average, interfaces combining lifeworld and political knowledge are the most present (Figure 35), and their spread shows a consistent presence and significance throughout the crisis (Table 70). While we don't know how much the lack of information during the COVID-19 pandemic caused this result, we do know that lifeworld knowledge will prove to be crucial for the formulation and implementation of public value solutions through the crisis.

Another interesting result comes from the spread of the interfaces between expert and political knowledge (Table 69). These were in fact mostly present in phase 1, underlining how it is still the first instinct of policymakers to rely on expert knowledge, but that this will not prove to be crucial except for a few cases. Finally, while the spread of interfaces combining the three knowledge types shows they are present, these are not clearly significant or crucial for the formulation and implementation of public value solutions.

Thus, to conclude, these findings direct our attention to lifeworld knowledge and the crucial role it played during the turbulence. At the same time, we see a declining presence of political knowledge and interfaces exclusively between political and expert knowledge mostly present in phase 1.

This evidence urges some further questions which could be addressed in the qualitative configurational analysis (QCA), such as:

- Under which conditions does the involvement of lifeworld knowledge become crucial?
- Under which conditions does the involvement of political knowledge decline?
- Under which conditions are lifeworld knowledge interfaces with political knowledge more present than those with expert knowledge?

3.3.1 Three different types of knowledge

Although we will present the findings for each type of knowledge in the upcoming sections, figure 31 presents an integrated overview of these types. Political knowledge is “knowledge about the political system, its institutions, processes, and actors,” (Russo & Van Dooren, 2023, p. 3).⁴ It is also strategic knowledge (*savoir faire*) about how to ensure parliamentary and public support for ideas and policies. Expert knowledge is “scientific knowledge, defined and aimed at predicting and controlling uncertainty,” (Russo & Van Dooren, 2023, p. 3).⁴ Expert knowledge is based on

⁵ Russo, C., & Van Dooren, W. (2023, August 30). *Framework for studying societal intelligence*.

scientifically accepted methods and styles of reasoning. Lifeworld knowledge is “tacit, local knowledge accumulated from everyday experience, including intuitions, assumptions, beliefs, and values,” (Russo & Van Dooren, 2023, p. 3).⁴ It often includes detailed knowledge of everyday practices, such as the working of neighborhoods, schools, local crime, or traffic problems. Lifeworld knowledge is based on tacit intuitions, locally tested assumptions, and strong normative values.

Figure 31. Integrated overview of types of knowledge during COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
Expert knowledge	0,35	0,35	0,36
Political knowledge	0,30	0,33	0,34
Lifeworld knowledge	0,36	0,32	0,37

Table 64. Standard deviations of the different types of knowledge.

In Figure 32, 33 and 34, the averages of the three types of knowledge over the three phases is visually displayed.

Figure 32. Averages of expert knowledge over the three phases of COVID-19.

In Table 65, the presence of expert knowledge is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	7	5	9
0.33 (present)	13	12	13
0.66 (present and significant)	7	7	5
1 (present, significant and crucial)	8	11	8
Total	35	35	35

Table 65. The presence of expert knowledge per phase.

Figure 33. Averages of political knowledge over the three phases of COVID-19.

In Table 66, the presence of political knowledge is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	7	10	13
0.33 (present)	9	11	9
0.66 (present and significant)	16	10	9
1 (present, significant and crucial)	3	4	4
Total	35	35	35

Table 66. The presence of political knowledge per phase.

Figure 34. Averages of lifeworld knowledge over the three phases of COVID-19.

In Table 67, the presence of lifeworld knowledge is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	4	3	6
0.33 (present)	6	4	5
0.66 (present and significant)	7	11	9
1 (present, significant and crucial)	18	17	15
Total	35	35	35

Table 67. The presence of lifeworld knowledge per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a specific type of knowledge was influencing the designing and/or delivering public value solutions throughout a certain phase. In this case, the type of knowledge was absent. Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude that public value solutions could not have come about without this specific type of knowledge. In this case, the type of knowledge was present, significant and crucial.

The integrated overview showcases how lifeworld knowledge was predominant throughout the different phases of COVID-19. When we take a more detailed look at the results, we observe expert knowledge is present in the formulation and implementation of a large number of public value

solutions, and significant or even crucial in some of the solutions that were studied. The data on political knowledge is scattered, as we see that the averages are dispersed. In a large number of cases, however, political knowledge is present or even significant. This points to the importance still played by local autonomy and hierarchy. Finally, the insights on lifeworld knowledge show how this type of knowledge has been crucial for many of the public value solutions that were examined. In some cases, this knowledge becomes significant in phase 2 of the crisis. However, please note that these interpretations are based on averages, which are accompanied by relatively high standard deviations. Therefore, the extent to which there is a variety across cases is relatively high.

3.3.2 Knowledge interfaces

Knowledge interfaces are “spaces where interaction between different types of knowledge takes place. In these spaces, knowledge is exchanged and developed, [...] exemplified by stakeholder relations [...] where complementary capabilities, competencies, and resources align,” (Russo & Van Dooren, 2023, pp. 4-14).¹⁷ In Figure 35, the different types of knowledge interfaces are visually displayed.

Figure 35. Knowledge interfaces during COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
Expert and political interface	0,29	0,33	0,33
Lifeworld and political interface	0,32	0,33	0,33
Expert and lifeworld interface	0,34	0,36	0,34
Lifeworld, expert and political interface	0,31	0,33	0,31

Table 68. Standard deviations for the knowledge interfaces.

In Tables 69, 70, 71, and 71, the presence of different knowledge interfaces is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	15	18	19
0.33 (present)	13	9	8
0.66 (present and significant)	5	5	5
1 (present, significant and crucial)	2	3	3
Total	35	35	35

Table 69. The presence of the expert and political interface per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	9	11	13
0.33 (present)	13	10	9
0.66 (present and significant)	9	10	10
1 (present, significant and crucial)	4	4	3
Total	35	35	35

Table 70. The presence of the lifeworld and political interface per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	14	14	16
0.33 (present)	11	9	10
0.66 (present and significant)	6	7	5
1 (present, significant and crucial)	4	5	4
Total	35	35	35

Table 71. The presence of the expert and lifeworld interface per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	18	19	19
0.33 (present)	9	8	8
0.66 (present and significant)	6	5	6
1 (present, significant and crucial)	2	3	2
Total	35	35	35

Table 72. The presence of the lifeworld, expert, and political interface per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude a certain type of knowledge interface occurred for the designing and/or delivering from the public value solution throughout a specific phase. In this case, the knowledge interface was absent. Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude that the public value solution could not have come about without a certain type of knowledge interface. In this case, the knowledge interface was present, significant and crucial. The findings show that different types of interfaces were present, but not significant in the

formulation and implementation of public value solutions throughout the different phases of COVID-19. The interfaces between lifeworld and political knowledge seem the most significant compared to other combinations, and also the most consistent throughout the crisis. However, please note that these interpretations are based on averages, which are accompanied by relatively high standard deviations. Therefore, the extent to which there is a variety across cases is relatively high.

Final reflection on confidence

Contributors deliver the outcomes regarding societal intelligence with significant confidence (score: 0.76 on a scale of 0 to 1). Interesting to note is that the contributors have filled out a score of 0.66 or a score of 1; the data show that scores of 0 or 0.33 were not assigned. Therefore, confidence levels can be perceived as relatively high.

Part IV. Report on the robustness of the response and fundamental values upheld (D6.3)

Societal turbulence is defined as “a situation where cascading and interrelated social, natural, economic, and political events, demands and developments unexpectedly create unpredictable temporal dynamics that jeopardize the preservation of core functions, goals, and values of society and/or particular sectors of society,” (Torfing et al., 2023, p. 16)⁵.

In the case of the COVID-pandemic, the rising turbulence was triggered by a health crisis. The rapidly rising number of infected people threatened the health care system that was on the brink of breaking down. Lockdowns and health regulations prevented the collapse of the health care system but made it impossible for children to go to school, attend leisure activities and see their friends. Hence, core public functions such as the provision of education and the ability to protect the welfare of children were undermined.

In the public value solutions that we studied, we measured the impact of rising societal turbulence by asking contributors to what extent core values, goals and functions pertaining to child wellbeing were jeopardized. To specify, contributors could distinguish whether it was the social skills, cognitive skills, mental health and physical health of children that were affected by lockdowns, school closings and staying at home. In this regard, our findings suggest mostly social skills and mental health were significantly jeopardized.

As governance responses affected societal trends and events, possibly inducing further turbulence, contributors were also requested to share insights on the measures that were taken to respond to the pandemic on the national, regional and local level. More specifically, contributors were requested to share insights on their outcomes.

Our findings suggest that, on average, the public value solutions we studied were significantly legitimate and effective, and avoided further turbulence. Many public value solutions also demonstrated adaptability, although this characteristic did not play a crucial role in all phases of the crisis. Innovativeness was evident in the early stages but diminished as the pandemic progressed. In the two following sections, we elaborate on different types of insights related to the robustness of the public value solutions that were formulated and implemented.

4.1. Societal turbulence

Societal turbulence is defined as “a situation where cascading and interrelated social, natural, economic, and political events, demands and developments unexpectedly create unpredictable temporal dynamics that jeopardize the preservation of core functions, goals, and values of society and/or particular sectors of society,” (Torfing et al., 2023, p. 16)⁶. In the case studies, we measured the level of societal turbulence by asking contributors to what extent core values, goals and functions regarding child wellbeing were jeopardized. To specify, contributors could distinguish between social skills, cognitive skills, mental health and physical health of children.

As governance responses affected societal trends and events, possibly inducing further turbulence, contributors were also requested to share insights on the measures that were taken to respond to the pandemic on the national, regional and local level. We elaborate on both types of insights in the two following sections.

⁶ Torfing, J., Sørensen, E., & Nielsen, R.O. (2023). *Proof of concept*.

Looking at the results so far, we see two key avenues for further questioning in the qualitative configurational analysis (QCA):

- How do the different outcome dimensions (effectiveness, legitimacy, etc.) occur together or fail to occur together (i.e. is there a trade-off or a positive link between outcome dimensions)?
- How does the presence or absence of the different governance factors and actor strategies correspond to the presence or absence of robust outcomes?

4.1.1. Jeopardization of core values, goals, and functions

In ROBUST, we distinguished between four core values, goals and functions regarding child wellbeing. Please consult table 73 for a further explanation of these.

Social skills	The skills to manage and understand other's and own emotions, maintain relationships with friends and family, and social awareness.
Cognitive skills	The educational development of children, including aspects such as performance in reading and math, as well as language development and problem-solving capacities.
Mental health	The emotional and psychological well-being of children. This encompasses how children think, feel, and behave, as well as their ability to cope with stress, manage emotions, and form healthy relationships.
Physical health	The overall well-being of a child's body and physical functioning. This encompasses factors such as nutrition, exercise, and sleep. Therefore, please note that physical health does not merely relate to the direct influence of COVID-19 infections on children.

Table 73. Definitions of core values, goals and functions regarding child wellbeing.

In figure 36, the extent to which children's social skills, cognitive skills, mental health and physical health were jeopardized due to COVID-19 is visually displayed. We distinguish between three phases of the pandemic.

Figure 36. The jeopardy of core values, goals and functions regarding child wellbeing during COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
Social skills	0,27	0,20	0,31
Cognitive skills	0,32	0,25	0,27
Mental health	0,27	0,23	0,30
Physical health	0,35	0,30	0,22

Table 74. Standard deviations of core values, goals and functions regarding child wellbeing.

In Tables 75, 76, 77, and 78, the jeopardy of core values, goals and functions is listed, distinguishing between the different phases of COVID-19.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	2	1	6
0.33 (present)	2	4	14
0.66 (present and significant)	14	25	10
1 (present, significant and crucial)	17	5	5
Total	35	35	35

Table 75. The jeopardy of social skills per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	3	2	7
0.33 (present)	6	12	20
0.66 (present and significant)	12	17	5
1 (present, significant and crucial)	14	4	3
Total	35	35	35

Table 76. The jeopardization of cognitive skills per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	2	0	4
0.33 (present)	2	6	12
0.66 (present and significant)	14	17	13
1 (present, significant and crucial)	17	12	6
Total	35	35	35

Table 77. The jeopardization of mental health per phase.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	11	12	15
0.33 (present)	13	16	18
0.66 (present and significant)	5	4	1
1 (present, significant and crucial)	6	3	1
Total	35	35	35

Table 78. The jeopardization of physical skills per phase.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude the value, goal or function was jeopardized due to COVID-19 throughout a specific phase, while score 1 would imply that the value, goal or function was gravely and critically jeopardized. The findings show that social skills and mental health were significantly jeopardized, while children’s physical health was affected to a lesser extent. However, please note that these interpretations are based on averages, which are accompanied by relatively high standard deviations. This showcases a variety across cases. Furthermore, contributing researchers rarely mention a difference in how threats affect different genders. Ultimately, contributors deliver these outcomes with significant confidence (score: 0.83 on a scale of 0 to 1).

4.1.2. Measures on national, regional, and local levels

Major events and actions at different levels and in different domains		
European level (pre-filled)	National level	Regional/local level
Outbreak and first wave of the COVID-19 virus		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> January 24, 2020: The first cases of COVID-19 were reported in Europe, initially in France. February 21, 2020: Cases started to escalate, with Italy becoming an early hotspot. March 17, 2020: Many EU countries implemented travel restrictions and border controls. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> February, 2020: first cases of COVID reported in all countries. March/April, 2020: most countries implement lockdown measures to combat the spread of COVID-19. This includes closure of schools, borders, restaurants and bars, and non-essential stores. May/June, 2020: most national governments start 	<p><i>In general, we observe that in most countries local measures correspond to the decisions made at the national level. However, a few countries show that the local/regional level could make different decisions. Especially in the beginning of the crisis, when local governmental</i></p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • March 24, 2020: The European Central Bank (ECB) announced a Pandemic Emergency Purchase Programme (PEPP) to stabilize financial markets. • April 20, 2020: 1.6 billion learners in 199 countries were affected by school closures, affecting not only their access to education but also their access to health, nutrition, and protection services. • July 21, 2020: EU leaders reached an agreement on a €750 billion recovery package, including the NextGenerationEU fund. 	<p>with phased reopening of schools, outdoor sports and businesses under strict and later, more loose, guidelines.</p>	<p><i>actors decided to implement restrictions for among others, cultural institutions, nurseries and child care, and public transport.</i></p> <p><i>Overall, we observe that the local/regional level is mostly involved in organizing policies/initiatives focussed on child wellbeing, facilitating testing on the COVID-19 virus and implementing and controlling restrictions, instead of formulating restrictions.</i></p>
Second wave of the COVID-19 virus		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • October 2020: Many European countries experienced a second surge in COVID-19 cases, leading to renewed concerns and additional lockdown measures. • December 27, 2020: The EU began its coordinated vaccination campaign, with the first doses administered to frontline healthcare workers and high-risk populations. • January 9, 2021: a new variant of the SARS-CoV-2 virus, the B.1.1.7 variant, is identified, prompting increased monitoring. • Early 2021: Some EU countries faced challenges in the distribution and administration of vaccines, including supply chain issues, logistical hurdles, and vaccine hesitancy. • May 2021: The Council of Europe urges member states to take action to address the impact of the COVID-19 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • October/November/December: due to the second wave of COVID-19, most countries start with new measures, such as compulsory use of face masks, school closures and a maximum number of people at certain places. • January: vaccination programs were rolled out in most European countries, initially for healthcare personnel and vulnerable groups of citizens • January/February: In some European countries measures were tightened, for example by implementing a curfew. • April, 2021: Countries were slowly re-opening by loosening the rules for schools and sports and allowing holiday travelling. • June 2021, in most European countries a large proportion of the population is vaccination, making it possible to loosen the restrictions more. • Most countries experience a 'normal summer'. Some of these countries did not 	<p><i>In general, we observe that in most countries local measures correspond to the decisions made at the national level. However, a few countries show that the local/regional level could make different decisions. Especially in the beginning of the crisis, when local governmental actors decided to implement restrictions for among others, cultural institutions, nurseries and child care, and public transport.</i></p> <p><i>Over all, we observe that the local/regional level is mostly involved in organizing policies/initiatives focussed on child wellbeing, facilitating testing on the COVID-19 virus and implementing and controlling</i></p>

<p>pandemic on the rights of children.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> July 1, 2021: The EU introduced the Digital COVID Travel Certificate. 	<p>implement new restrictions which impacted children after the summer, others did.</p>	<p><i>restrictions, instead of formulating restrictions.</i></p>
Remainder of the COVID-19 virus		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> August 31, 2021: continued vaccination efforts led to 70 percent of adults in the EU being vaccinated. October 4, 2021: EMA recommends adjusting vaccination strategies by adding 'booster shots'. December 2021: Booster shot campaigns initiated in some EU countries. January 2022: UNICEF warns the scale of education loss due to COVID-19 is 'nearly insurmountable', with younger children facing the greatest loss. Early 2022: more and more recovery plans from European member states are approved, leading to increasing usage of the EU recovery and resilience funds. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> September 2021: a new variant of COVID-19, the omikron variant was discovered. November 2021: Multiple countries start using the 'vaccination or recovered rule', which limited the access of non-vaccinated to hotels, restaurants and other places. December 2021: in a few countries schools were closed again, in others there were no restrictions. January, 2022: some corona measures were loosened for schools, sports and other recreational activities. February/March, 2022: in most countries all corona rules are abolished. 	<p><i>In general, we observe that in most countries local measures correspond to the decisions made at the national level. However, a few countries show that the local/regional level could make different decisions. Especially in the beginning of the crisis, when local governmental actors decided to implement restrictions for among others, cultural institutions, nurseries and child care, and public transport.</i></p> <p><i>Over all, we observe that the local/regional level is mostly involved in organizing policies/initiatives focussed on child wellbeing, facilitating testing on the COVID-19 virus and implementing and controlling restrictions, instead of formulating restrictions.</i></p>

4.2 Initial reflections on robustness

4.2.1. Legitimacy of public value solutions

Legitimacy refers to the extent to which public value solutions secured support among stakeholders. In table 79, the legitimacy of public value solutions over the three phases is listed.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	6	1	5
0.33 (present)	1	3	4

0.66 (present and significant)	13	16	11
1 (present, significant and exceeding)	15	15	15
Total	35	35	35

Table 79. Legitimacy of public value solutions over the three phases

In Figures 37 and 38, the averages and trends of the legitimacy of public value solutions over the three phases is visually displayed.

Figure 37. Averages of the legitimacy of public value solutions over the three phases of COVID-19.

Figure 38. The trends of the legitimacy of public value solutions over the three phases of COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0,36	0,25	0,35

Table 80. Standard deviations for the legitimacy of the public value solutions.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude the public value solution was legitimate in at least some extent throughout a specific phase. In this case, the result was absent. Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution affected legitimacy beyond the initially intended ambitions of the initiators throughout a specific phase. In this case, the result was present, significant and exceeding. The findings show the mode of the legitimacy is 1.0, which implies a large number of the public value solutions that were examined were significantly legitimate and even exceeded the initial intended ambitions of the initiators. Moreover, the trend in figure 38 shows the public value solutions were significantly legitimate throughout the different phases of COVID-19, with a minor peak during the second phase of the pandemic. However, please note that these interpretations are mostly based on averages, which are accompanied by relatively high standard deviations. This showcases a variety across cases.

4.2.2. Effectiveness of public value solutions

Effectiveness concerns the extent to which public value solutions achieved their stated goals. In table 81, the effectiveness of public value solutions over the three phases is listed.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>

0 (absent)	6	1	5
0.33 (present)	4	4	3
0.66 (present and significant)	16	18	17
1 (present, significant and exceeding)	9	12	10
Total	35	35	35

Table 81. Effectiveness of public value solutions over the three phases

In Figures 39 and 40, the averages and trends of the effectiveness of public value solutions over the three phases is visually displayed.

Figure 39. Averages of the effectiveness of public value solutions over the three phases of COVID-19.

Figure 40. The trends of the effectiveness of public value solutions over the three phases of COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0,34	0,25	0,32

Table 82. Standard deviations for the effectiveness of the public value solutions.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude the public value solution was effective in at least some extent throughout a specific phase. In this case, the result was absent. Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution affected effectiveness beyond the initially intended ambitions of the initiators throughout a specific phase. In this case, the result was present, significant and exceeding. The findings show the mode of the effectiveness is 0.66, which implies most of the public value solutions were significantly effective. Moreover, the trend in figure 40 shows the public value solutions were effective throughout the different phases of COVID-19, and significantly effective during the second phase and the remainder. However, please note that these interpretations are mostly based on averages, which are accompanied by relatively high standard deviations. This showcases a variety across cases.

4.2.3. Adaptiveness of public value solutions

Adaptiveness refers to the extent to which existing policies and initiatives were modified to fit new and changing problems and situations. Adaptation involves modifying something that was already

there without producing new solutions based on new ideas. In table 83, the adaptiveness of public value solutions over the three phases is listed.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	7	3	7
0.33 (present)	4	9	11
0.66 (present and significant)	19	18	14
1 (present, significant and exceeding)	5	5	3
Total	35	35	35

Table 83. Adaptiveness of public value solutions over the three phases

In Figures 41 and 42, the averages and trends of the adaptiveness of public value solutions over the three phases is visually displayed.

Figure 41. Averages of the adaptiveness of public value solutions over the three phases of COVID-19.

Figure 42. The trends of the adaptiveness of public value solutions over the three phases of COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0,32	0,27	0,30

Table 84. Standard deviations for the adaptiveness of the public value solutions.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude the public value solution was adaptive in at least some extent throughout a specific phase. In this case, the result was absent. Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution affected adaptiveness beyond the initially intended ambitions of the initiators throughout a specific phase. In this case, the result was present, significant and exceeding. The findings show the mode of the adaptiveness is 0.66, which implies a relatively large number of the public value solutions were significantly adaptive. However, the averages that are presented in figure 42 show how adaptiveness was present in the public value solutions, but did not play a significant role throughout the different phases of COVID-19. However, please note that these interpretations are mostly based on averages, which are accompanied by relatively high standard deviations. This showcases a variety across cases.

4.2.4. Innovativeness of public value solutions

Innovativeness concerns the extent to which new creative solutions that break with common wisdom and established practices that were developed and implemented. Innovation involves a disruption of existing practices and the development and implementation of new solutions based on new ideas

and understandings. In table 85 the innovativeness of public value solutions over the three phases is listed.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	10	7	11
0.33 (present)	5	7	10
0.66 (present and significant)	14	16	9
1 (present, significant and exceeding)	6	5	5
Total	35	35	35

Table 85. Innovativeness of public value solutions over the three phases

In Figures 43 and 44, the averages and trends of the innovativeness of public value solutions over the three phases is visually displayed.

Figure 43. Averages of the innovativeness of public value solutions over the three phases of COVID-19.

Figure 44. The trends of the innovativeness of public value solutions over the three phases of COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0,36	0,32	0,35

Table 86. Standard deviations for the innovativeness of the public value solutions.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude the public value solution was innovative in at least some extent throughout a specific phase. In this case, the result was absent. Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution affected innovativeness beyond the initially intended ambitions of the initiators throughout a specific phase. In this case, the result was present, significant and exceeding. The findings show the mode of the innovativeness is 0.66 in the first two waves of the pandemic, which implies a relatively large number of the public value solutions were significantly innovative in that stage. In the remainder of the crisis, however, the mode is 0, which implies innovativeness was absent. Moreover, the averages that are presented in figure 44 show how innovativeness was present in the public value solutions, but did not play a significant role throughout the different phases of COVID-19. However, please note that these interpretations are mostly based on averages, which are accompanied by relatively high standard deviations. This showcases a variety across cases.

4.2.5. Avoiding accelerating further turbulence

If public value solutions avoided accelerating further turbulence, the accompanying actions did not lead to more threats to the core values, goals, and functions of governance. In table 87, the extent to which public value solutions avoided accelerating further turbulence over the three phases is listed.

	<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0 (absent)	3	1	5
0.33 (present)	6	4	4
0.66 (present and significant)	13	15	11
1 (present, significant and exceeding)	13	15	15
Total	35	35	35

Table 87. Extent to which public value solutions avoided accelerating further turbulence over the three phases

In Figures 45 and 46, the averages and trends of the extent to which public value solutions avoided accelerating further turbulence over the three phases is visually displayed.

Figure 45. Averages of the extent to which public value solutions avoided accelerating further turbulence over the three phases of COVID-19.

Figure 46. The trends of the extent to which public value solutions avoided accelerating further turbulence over the three phases of COVID-19.

The averages are accompanied by the following standard deviations:

<i>Phase 1</i>	<i>Phase 2</i>	<i>Remainder</i>
0,31	0,26	0,35

Table 88. Standard deviations for the extent to which public value solutions avoided accelerating further turbulence.

Score 0 would imply that there is no sufficient evidence to conclude the public value solution was avoiding accelerating further turbulence in at least some extent throughout a specific phase. In this case, the result was absent. Score 1 would imply that there is evidence to conclude the public value solution was avoiding accelerating further turbulence beyond the initially intended ambitions of the initiators throughout a specific phase. In this case, the result was present, significant and exceeding. The findings show the mode of this characteristic is 1.0 in the remainder of the crisis, which implies most of the public value solutions did not accelerate further turbulence by then and even exceeded the initial intended ambitions of the initiators in this regard. For wave one and two, the findings show how the public value solutions did not accelerate further turbulence, but did not exceed the initial ambitions. The trend in figure 46 confirms these findings and shows the public value solutions did not accelerate further turbulence throughout the different phases of COVID-19. However, please note that these interpretations are mostly based on averages, which are accompanied by relatively high standard deviations. This showcases a variety across cases.

4.2.6. Reflections on robustness of public value solutions

All in all, the five different characteristics of robustness were present throughout the different phases of COVID-19, although not all of them were significant. In figure 47, we present an integrated overview of the different characteristics of robust governance.

Figure 47. Initial reflections on robustness of public value solutions during COVID-19.

Final reflection on confidence

Contributors deliver these outcomes with significant confidence (score: 0.83 on a scale of 0 to 1). Interesting to note is that the contributors have filled out a score of 0.66 or a score of 1; the data show that scores of 0 or 0.33 were not assigned. Therefore, confidence levels can be perceived as relatively high.

Part V. Coded data set of cases showing the different configurations (D7.1)

In line with the European ambitions on free and open data and to support the reuse of the data, the full case study dataset will be made publicly available under the FAIR principles at the end of the project. The dataset is stored on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14989122>⁷

We present the data in two common formats: a spreadsheet containing all the data in a systematic overview and a collection of the case reports in PDF format.

In addition, the Zenodo record contains machine readable metadata that conforms to the CESSDA approach to implementation the FAIR principles, i.e., documenting the variables measured and method used in machine readable form⁸. The Zenodo platform automatically makes the metadata findable for machine readers in a variety of recognized formats, e.g., the Dublin Core format.

⁷ For the purposes of this deliverable, the data is uploaded to a space with restricted access. For purposes of review, access to the data can be granted by the coordinator. Access restrictions will be lifted immediately upon the final approval of the deliverable.

⁸ Please note that the metadata will be finalized as part of D1.4 Open Datasets in September 2025.